

RESOLUTION OF $\alpha\gamma$ -DIPHENYLGLUTACONIC ACID

BY G. M. KELKAR, N. L. PHALNIKAR AND B. V. BHIDE

$\alpha\gamma$ -Diphenylglutaconic acid has been resolved into *d*- and *l*-forms by the fractional precipitation of its strychnine salt. The *dextro*-form has not been obtained in an optically pure condition. The acids could not be racemised by heating with hydrochloric acid or sodium hydroxide. Melting racemises the acids. Attempts to convert *trans*- $\alpha\gamma$ -diphenylglutaconic acid into *cis*-acid according to the method of Feist have been found to be unsuccessful.

In order to explain some of the peculiarities of glutaconic acid Thorpe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 1669) proposed a normal structure for the stable form. Feist and his co-workers (*Annalen*, 1906, 345, 60) had criticised the theory of normal structure and tried to prove the molecular asymmetry of the acid by optical resolution of a number of glutaconic acids; but all such attempts at resolving the glutaconic acids (open-chain) were unsuccessful, though Feist (*Annalen*, 1924, 436, 135) resolved a cyclic glutaconic acid viz. 3-methylcyclopropene-1:2-dicarboxylic acid

However, the normal structure had to be finally discarded as $\alpha\gamma$ -dimethylglutaconic acid was resolved into optically active forms and hence its asymmetrical structure was proved (McCombs, Packer and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 547). The $\alpha\gamma$ -dimethylglutaconic acid was the first open-chain acid to be resolved into optically active forms.

In the present work the asymmetrical character of glutaconic acids has been further proved by the resolution of $\alpha\gamma$ -diphenylglutaconic acid. This acid (Phalnikar and Nargund, *J. Univ. Bomb.*, 1930, 7, iii, 203) was resolved into optically active forms through its strychnine salt following the method of McCombs *et al.* (*loc. cit.*). The *d*-form could not be obtained in an optically pure form having a rotation equal to that of the *l*-form. A similar observation has been noted in the case of $\alpha\gamma$ -dimethylglutaconic acid by McCombs *et al.* (*loc. cit.*). The $\alpha\gamma$ -diphenylglutaconic acid could not be racemised by heating for four hours with hydrochloric acid or sodium hydroxide, but the acid easily racemised on heating above its melting point (235°). It may be noted that $\alpha\gamma$ -dimethylglutaconic acid readily racemises by boiling with hydrochloric acid or sodium hydroxide (McCombs *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). Another peculiarity of the acid is that it has two distinct melting points. It first melts at 180° and again becomes solid and on further heating melts at 233°.

$\alpha\gamma$ -Diphenylglutaconic acid is most probably a *trans*-acid, although there is no definite evidence in this direction. Attempts are described in the experimental part to convert it into the *cis*-form. $\alpha\gamma$ -Dimethylglutaconic acid, prepared and resolved by Thorpe is regarded as a *trans*-acid. The *cis*-form of this acid has not been isolated.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Resolution of α -Diphenylglutaconic Acid

α -Diphenylglutaconic acid was prepared according to the method of Phalnikar and Nargund (*loc. cit.*).

The method followed for resolving the acid was similar to the one used by McCombs *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) in resolving α -dimethylglutaconic acid. Strychnine ($\frac{1}{4}$ equivalent) was dissolved in chloroform and was added to a cold solution of the acid (4 equivalents) in ether. The precipitated strychnine salt was filtered after half an hour and the precipitate and filtrates were collected separately. The precipitated salt was washed with a mixture of chloroform and ether, and then decomposed by shaking with *N*-ammonia and the solution extracted with chloroform four times to remove all the strychnine. The ammoniacal salt solution of the acid was then decomposed with *N*-hydrochloric acid and the precipitated acid was taken up in ether. The ether layer was washed, dried and ether removed as usual. The residual acid was taken in a beaker and was dried in a vacuum desiccator, weighed and its rotation was found from the 1% solution of the acid in ethyl alcohol. This acid obtained in the first precipitation was fractionally reprecipitated a number of times till the final precipitated acid showed a constant rotation.

A Stanley-Belingham precision type polarimeter with an accuracy of 0.01 degree in sodium light was used. The determinations were carried out in all the cases with a 2 dm. tube at 25°. Absolute alcohol was used for preparing the solutions. Concentration of the solution was 1% (vol.) in each case. Table I summarises the results.

TABLE I

Inactive acid (6 g.)	
Precipitate (I) (2.619 g.)	Filtrate (3.391 g.) $[\alpha]_D^{25} = - (50)$ Combined filtrates (Total weight, 4.391 g.)
Precipitate (II) (1.833 g.) $[\alpha]_D^{25} = - (290)$	Filtrate (0.7 g.)
Precipitate (III) (1.263 g.) $[\alpha]_D^{25} = - (310)$	Filtrate
Precipitate (IV) (0.8620 g.) $[\alpha]_D^{25} = - (350)$	Filtrate (0.3 g.) $[\alpha]_D^{25} = - (254)$
Precipitate (V) (0.5006 g.) $[\alpha]_D^{25} = - (350)$	Filtrate (0.2 g.) $[\alpha]_D^{25} = - (350)$
M.p. of the acid, 187—190° and then 233—35°.	

M.p. of strychnine salt, 177°—180°;

M.p. of acid, 187—90° and then 233—35°

After the fifth precipitation the specific rotation of the acid from the filtrate and of the acid from the precipitated strychnine salt was identical (-350). This shows that the substance was obtained as a pure *laevo*-form.

The filtrate was also subjected to the same treatment in order to obtain the pure *d*-form of the acid, but after the third precipitation it was found that the acid had a rotation which could not be increased by further fractional precipitation. Thus the *d*-form obtained was optically impure. Table II summarises the results.

TABLE II

Combined filtrates (4 g.) $[\alpha]_D^{25} = + (50)$	
Filtrate I (1.14 g.) $[\alpha]_D^{25} = + (120)$	Precipitate (2.8 g.)
Filtrate II (0.7 g.) $[\alpha]_D^{25} = + (120)$	Precipitate (0.35 g.) $[\alpha]_D^{25} = + (120)$
(M. p. of the acid, $187-90^\circ$ and then 233°). (M. p. of the acid, $187-90^\circ$ and then 233°)	

As after the second precipitation, the specific rotation of the acid from the precipitate was the same $+ (120)$ as that from the filtrate, no further separation was assumed to be possible.

Racemisation Experiments

(A) *Boiling with sodium hydroxide.*—*L*-Acid (0.5 g.) was dissolved in 5 c.c. of *N*-sodium hydroxide solution and boiled for 4 hours. The acid was recovered from the sodium salt as usual and its rotation was found. $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ of the recovered acid = $-(345)$ and that of the original acid = $-(350)$.

This shows that after boiling with sodium hydroxide no racemisation takes place.

(B) *Boiling with hydrochloric acid.*—*L*-Acid (0.25 g.) was boiled for 4 hours with 25 c. c. of *N*-hydrochloric acid. The acid was then filtered, washed with a little water, dried and its rotations measured as $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -(350)$, thus proving that there was no racemisation.

(C) *Synthetic racemic forms.*—*d*-Acid (0.125 g.) and *l*-acid (0.04285 g.) were dissolved in alcohol. The solution was allowed to stand for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The resulting acid was found to be optically inactive.

The *laevo* acid was melted and kept at 235° for 15 minutes. After cooling it was found to be completely inactive. The *dextro*-acid also completely racemised when treated in the same way.

Attempts to convert trans- $\alpha\gamma$ -Diphenylglutaconic Acid to cis-Acid

The anhydride of the acid (m. p. $118-19^\circ$) was hydrolysed by the method followed by Feist (*Annalen*, 1909, 370, 41) for conversion of $\alpha\gamma$ -dimethylglutaconic acid from *trans* to *cis*.

Equivalent quantities of the anhydride and casein were mixed and heated with *N*/10 sodium hydroxide solution. It was then kept at room temperature for 3 days till the solution became slightly acidio. It was precipitated with silver nitrate. The silver salt was filtered, suspended in dry ether and through it dry H_2S was passed. The precipitate of silver sulphide was filtered off, and the acid, after removing the ether, was crystallised. Its melting point was found to be $175-80^\circ$ and then $230-33^\circ$ thus proving that no conversion was effected.

MAHARAJA PRATAPSIKH CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
SIR PARSHURAMBHAU COLLEGE, POONA.

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